

Biological Clock and Academic Affect: Assessing the Impact of Chronotype on Student Subjective Wellbeing

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Abstract

Adolescence involves a biological shift toward eveningness, often causing misalignment with early school schedules. This study explored the relationship between chronotype and student subjective wellbeing. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, data were gathered from 267 Grade 11 and 12 students in Misamis Occidental, Philippines. Chronotypes were identified using the MEQ-REV-SA, while the SSWQ measured student subjective wellbeing and its four dimensions. Results showed that most learners (53.6%) possessed an intermediate chronotype, reflecting a balanced biological preference. Furthermore, students reported high levels of subjective wellbeing, particularly regarding educational purpose. Pearson's correlation revealed no statistically significant relationship between chronotype and any wellbeing dimension. These findings suggest that chronological predisposition does not meaningfully correlate with the learner's sense of purpose, efficacy, or connectedness in the schooling context. The prevalence of the intermediate chronotype may act as a buffer against social jetlag, allowing students to adapt effectively to traditional school timings. Consequently, school-based factors may influence adolescent wellbeing more profoundly than innate chronobiological rhythms.

Keywords: Chronotype, Student Subjective Wellbeing, Senior High School, Chronobiology, MEQ, SSWQ

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1. Introduction

Adolescence is a critical developmental period marked by major biological and psychological transitions, including changes in sleep preferences and daily activity timing known as chronotypes. Chronotype, which is shaped by a combination of individual, environmental, and social factors, reflects an individual's innate biological preference for the timing of sleep and activity, regulated by the circadian rhythm (Chauhan et al., 2023; Karan et al., 2021). This 24-hour internal clock governs essential physiological processes and determines an individual's peak alertness and activity levels throughout the day (Shimura, 2020; Sultana, 2024). Individuals are generally classified as morning, evening, or intermediate types based on these innate schedules.

Research indicates that during adolescence, there is a prominent developmental shift toward eveningness, typically peaking between the ages of 14 and 19 (Rodríguez Ferrante & Leone, 2024; Verma et al., 2021). This biological delay often clashes with the early start times of traditional school systems, leading to social jetlag – a misalignment between an adolescent's internal biological clock and the external demands of their social and academic schedule (Bouman & Rutters, 2022; Caliandro et al., 2021). This misalignment has been linked to inadequate nutrient intake, increased sedentary behavior, and higher levels of depressive and anxiety symptoms (Saxvig et al., 2021; Tamura et al., 2021). Furthermore, while morning-type learners often exhibit superior academic performance, those with an evening chronotype frequently face challenges such as daytime sleepiness, reduced sleep duration, and higher rates of grade retention (Rodríguez Ferrante et al., 2023; Morrison et al., 2020).

Despite the well-documented deficits associated with later chronotypes, there is a growing imperative to move beyond a deficit-based model and toward a positive psychology perspective (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Renshaw et al., 2015). This approach emphasizes cultivating strengths and conditions that enable students to thrive rather than solely addressing psychological distress. At the center of this perspective is

Student Subjective Wellbeing (SSW), defined as a learner's self-perceived quality of life within the school context, encompassing both emotional and cognitive evaluations of their educational experiences (Renshaw, 2016). According to the framework established by Renshaw et al. (2015), SSW is a multidimensional construct comprising four key pillars: joy of learning, school connectedness, educational purpose, and academic efficacy.

Although extensive research has examined the links between chronotype and clinical psychopathology or raw academic scores, there remains a significant gap in understanding how biological preferences correlate with these specific dimensions of school-based wellbeing (Poon et al., 2024). Understanding whether a student's natural chronotype influences their sense of purpose, belonging, or confidence in an academic environment is crucial for creating supportive educational systems that align with adolescents' biological needs (Digdon & Howell, 2008).

The present study seeks to address this gap by examining the relationship between chronotypes and subjective wellbeing among senior high school learners in a public secondary school setting. By utilizing the Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire, Revised Self-Assessment Version (MEQ-REV-SA) (Terman et al., 2001) to identify individual chronotypes and the Student Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire (SSWQ) (Renshaw, 2018) to measure school-based wellbeing, this research aims to establish how chronological predispositions correlate with students' overall emotional and academic health. The findings are expected to provide evidence-based insights to inform school policies, optimize learning schedules, and enhance the delivery of personalized psychosocial support and guidance services, ultimately fostering holistic adolescent development.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design to investigate the relationship between chronotype and subjective wellbeing among senior high school learners. This approach was selected to determine the degree of association between variables without experimental manipulation, allowing for a precise statistical analysis of how natural biological predispositions relate to student psychological outcomes.

2.2. Research Environment and Participants

The study was conducted in a public secondary trade school located in urban Misamis Occidental, Philippines, which follows a standard Department of Education schedule of 7:30 a.m. to 4:30 p.m. The participants consisted of 267 senior high school (SHS) learners (136 from Grade 11 and 131 from Grade 12) enrolled during School Year 2025–2026. A stratified sampling technique was utilized to ensure proportional representation based on grade level and sex, minimizing selection bias and enhancing the generalizability of the findings within the local context.

2.3. Research Instruments

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, two validated self-report instruments were utilized:

- *Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire, Revised Self-Assessment Version (MEQ-REV-SA)* (Renshaw, 2018): This 19-item tool was used to identify individual

chronotypes based on preferred timing for sleep and daily activities. Scores range from 16 to 86, categorizing learners into five types: definite evening (16–30), moderate evening (31–41), intermediate (42–58), moderate morning (59–69), and definite morning (70–86). The MEQ-REV-SA maintains the robust psychometric properties of the original instrument while offering improved clarity for adolescent populations.

- *Student Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire (SSWQ)* (Terman et al., 2001): This measure assesses school-based wellbeing across four key dimensions: joy of learning, school connectedness, educational purpose, and academic efficacy. The SSWQ has demonstrated high internal consistency (overall $\alpha = .88$) and stability over time (Renshaw & Arslan, 2016), making it a reliable tool for measuring a learner's self-perceived quality of life in an academic setting.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Saint Columban College Research Ethics Committee, and formal permissions were secured from the school administration and instrument developers. Before data collection, participants and their guardians (for those under 18) provided informed consent and/or assent. The instruments were administered in-person using a paper-based modality. To ensure comprehension, the researcher read each item aloud and provided oral translations into the vernacular. Responses were verified for completeness before being encoded and stored securely.

2.5. Data Analysis

The gathered data were analyzed using JASP and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics, including count, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize chronotype distributions and levels of subjective wellbeing. To examine the relationship between chronotype (MEQ scores) and the dimensions of student subjective wellbeing (SSWQ scores), Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was calculated. The null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

The study strictly adhered to the APA (2016) Ethical Principles of Psychologists and Code of Conduct and the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173). Key protocols included ensuring confidentiality and anonymity, maintaining voluntary participation with the right to withdraw at any time, and guaranteeing the fair treatment of all participants regardless of their chronotype or academic track.

3. Results

3.1. Distribution of Chronotypes

Descriptive analysis of the Morningness-Eveningness Questionnaire (MEQ-REV-SA) scores indicated that the senior high school learners predominantly exhibited an intermediate chronotype. The mean MEQ score for the sample was 53.891 ($SD = 9.848$), which falls within the established intermediate range of 42 to 58. See Table 1 on the next page.

Table 1. *Learners' Chronotype*

Responses	Mean	SD	Chronotype Range	Interpretation
267	53.891	9.848	42 – 58	Intermediate Chronotype

Note: Chronotype range 16 – 30 = Definite Evening; 31 – 41 = Moderate Evening; 42 – 58 = Intermediate; 59 – 69 = Moderate Morning; 70 – 86 = Definite Morning

Of the 267 participants, 143 individuals (53.6%) were classified as intermediate types, suggesting a balanced biological preference that is neither distinctly morning- nor evening-oriented. This suggests that most students involved in the study do not have extreme sleeping or waking tendencies. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Distribution of Learners' Chronotype*

3.2. Levels of Student Subjective Wellbeing

The results from the Student Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire (SSWQ) revealed that the learners maintained a moderate to high level of school-based wellbeing. The overall mean score for Student Subjective Wellbeing (SSW) was 44.640 ($SD = 7.095$), falling within the "Often" range (40–55), which indicates that students frequently experience positive psychological states at school. See Table 2.

Table 2. *Learners' Student Subjective Wellbeing*

Dimension	Responses	Mean	SD	SW Range	Interpretation
Joy of Learning (JL)	267	10.022	7.095	10 – 13	Often
School Connectedness (SC)	267	10.577	2.352	10 – 13	Often
Educational Purpose (EP)	267	13.468	2.413	14 – 16	Often
Academic Efficacy (AE)	267	10.573	2.447	10 – 13	Often
Student Subjective Wellbeing (SSW)	267	44.640	2.466	40 – 55	Often

Note: JL, SC, EP, AE interpretation: 4 – 5 = Almost Never; 6 – 9 = Sometimes; 10 – 13 = Often; 14 – 16 = Almost Always
 SSW interpretation: 16 – 23 = Almost Never; 24 – 39 = Sometimes; 40 – 55 = Often; 56 – 64 = Almost Always

Analysis of the four specific dimensions showed that Educational Purpose (EP) yielded the highest mean score ($M = 13.468, SD = 2.413$), with students "almost always" perceiving their academic activities as meaningful and aligned with personal goals. This was followed by School Connectedness (SC) ($M = 10.577, SD = 2.413$) and Academic Efficacy (AE) ($M = 10.573, SD = 2.466$), both of which were interpreted as occurring "often". While Joy of Learning (JL) received the lowest relative score ($M = 10.022, SD = 2.352$), it remained within the positive "Often" range of the scale. See Figure 2.

Figure 2. Levels of Learners' Student Subjective Wellbeing

3.3. Relationship Between Chronotype and Student Subjective Wellbeing

To test the primary hypothesis, Pearson’s correlation coefficients (r) were calculated to examine the associations between chronotype scores and the dimensions of subjective wellbeing. The analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between the learners' chronotype and any aspect of their student subjective wellbeing.

Table 3. Relationship between Chronotype and SSW

Dimension	Pearson's <i>r</i>	Interpretation	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
Joy of Learning (JL)	0.058	Negligible	0.342	Not Significant
School Connectedness (SC)	0.054	Negligible	0.382	Not Significant
Academic Efficacy (AE)	0.065	Negligible	0.290	Not Significant
Educational Purpose (EP)	0.016	Negligible	0.791	Not Significant
Student Subjective Wellbeing (SSW)	0.066	Negligible	0.284	Not Significant

Note: Significance level is set to $p = 0.05$

Pearson's *r* scale: (-).90 to (-)1.00 = Very High correlation; (-).70 to (-).90 = High correlation; (-).50 to (-).70 = Moderate correlation; (-).30 to (-).50 = Low correlation; .00 to (-).30 = Negligible correlation

As shown in the statistical output in Table 3, the correlations across all dimensions were negligible. Because all *p*-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between chronotype and student subjective wellbeing could not be rejected. These findings suggest that for this population, biological timing does not meaningfully predict or influence a learner's sense of purpose, connectedness, efficacy, or joy within the academic environment.

4. Discussion

The findings regarding the distribution of chronotypes among the senior high school learners revealed that the majority of participants possessed an intermediate chronotype. This prevalence of intermediate chronotypes aligns with certain international studies, such as those by Saxvig et al. (2021) and Miño et al. (2025), which reported that approximately 48.4% to 52.3% of adolescent populations fall into this category. However, these results notably contrast with a significant body of existing research that documents a pronounced developmental shift toward eveningness during adolescence. Normative patterns typically suggest that biological rhythms delay significantly between the ages of 14 and 19, peaking in eveningness before reverting toward morningness in adulthood. Given that the participants in this study were aged 15 to 19, a stronger inclination toward eveningness was expected; therefore, the observed intermediate average represents a deviation from these normative developmental trends.

The predominance of the intermediate chronotype in this specific population suggests that these learners may be naturally more adaptable to traditional school schedules, such as the 7:30 a.m. to 4:30 p.m. routine followed by the study site. From a chronobiological perspective, this intermediate positioning may serve as a buffer against the negative outcomes typically associated with extreme eveningness, such as chronic sleep debt and social jetlag. Because these students do not face the extreme misalignment between their internal biological clocks and external academic demands, they may avoid the cognitive and emotional impairments often observed in "night owl" or late chronotype adolescents. Consequently, the lack of extreme circadian preferences in

this group may explain why chronotype did not emerge as a significant predictor of their subjective wellbeing.

Moreover, the assessment of Student Subjective Wellbeing (SSW) among the senior high school learners revealed a moderate to high level of school-based wellbeing, with an overall mean score of 44.640 ($SD = 7.095$). This finding suggests that learners generally maintain a favorable perception of their educational quality of life as students.

A closer examination of the four specific SSW dimensions revealed that Educational Purpose (EP) yielded the highest score (13.468), followed by School Connectedness (SC) (10.577), then Academic Efficacy (AE) (10.573), and lastly, Joy of Learning (JL) being the lowest (10.022) but still indicating that the learners still often experience or feel positive wellbeing.

These results are highly consistent with both local and international literature. The findings align with Galvez et al. (2023), who observed high levels of subjective wellbeing among secondary students in the Philippines. They also correspond with data from Serrão et al. (2024) regarding Portuguese adolescents (mean score of 43.34) and Azzahrah et al. (2024), who found moderate wellbeing levels among vocational learners in Indonesia.

Collectively, these scores support the positive psychology framework central to this study, which defines wellbeing not merely as the absence of distress but as the presence of positive psychological resources. The strong sense of educational purpose and connectedness observed suggests that the school environment successfully fosters strengths and meaningful experiences, which may act as a buffer for students regardless of their biological predispositions. These findings reinforce the idea that school-based wellbeing is a robust and positive construct among adolescents in this academic setting.

Lastly, the analysis of the relationship between chronotypes and student subjective wellbeing among senior high school learners yielded no statistically significant correlations across any of the measured dimensions. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which posited that no significant relationship exists between sleep-wake patterns and student subjective wellbeing, could not be rejected. These results indicate that, within this specific population, a learner's natural biological preference for sleep and activity does not meaningfully predict their emotional or cognitive evaluation of their school experience.

These findings present a notable contrast to much of the existing literature, which frequently highlights the negative psychosocial and academic outcomes associated with later (evening) chronotypes. Previous studies have often linked eveningness to higher levels of depressive symptoms, anxiety, and lower life satisfaction. For instance, research by Carciofo (2022) and Maultsby et al. (2022) established clear links between chronotype and mental health outcomes in adolescents. However, the present data suggest that such associations may not inherently extend to subjective wellbeing within the school context, particularly when examined through the multidimensional lens of the Student Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire (SSWQ).

One primary explanation for this lack of correlation is the predominance of the intermediate chronotype in this sample. Because the majority of participants (53.6%) fall near the midpoint of the circadian spectrum, they likely possess a degree of biological flexibility that allows them to adapt to the traditional 7:30 a.m. to 4:30 p.m. school schedule without experiencing extreme "social jetlag." This intermediate positioning likely acts as a

buffer, preventing the severe circadian misalignment that typically leads to the cognitive and emotional impairments observed in "night owl" students. Furthermore, as noted by Tokur-Kesgin and Kocoglu-Tanyer (2021), the relationship between chronotype and mental health is often mediated by external factors such as sleep quality, sleep duration, and academic stress, which were not the primary focus of this correlational analysis.

From a theoretical perspective, these results suggest a compelling interplay between chronobiology and positive psychology. While biological rhythms are fundamental to adolescent development, the high levels of wellbeing reported by learners, particularly regarding their sense of educational purpose, suggest that the school environment may play a more dominant role than biology alone. This implies that supportive school climates, meaningful learning experiences, and positive peer and teacher relationships may exert a greater influence on a student's sense of belonging and efficacy than their innate sleep-wake preferences. Ultimately, the study concludes that while circadian timing remains a factor in adolescent health, it does not strictly dictate a student's ability to thrive and find meaning within their educational journey.

5. Conclusion

Crucially, the statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between chronotype and any dimension of student subjective wellbeing. This suggests that the learner's natural chronological predisposition does not meaningfully predict their emotional or cognitive evaluation of the school experience. The lack of correlation may be attributed to the biological flexibility of the intermediate chronotype, which likely allows students to adapt to traditional school schedules without the severe "social jetlag" often experienced by extreme evening types.

Ultimately, this research concludes that school-based factors such as supportive relationships, academic engagement, and a clear sense of educational purpose exert a more profound influence on adolescent wellbeing than innate biological rhythms alone. These insights suggest that educational policies and guidance services should prioritize holistic support systems that address stress management, emotional regulation, and academic motivation to foster optimal development for all learners, regardless of their individual chronotypes.

However, the generalizability of the findings of this study is influenced by several limitations. One of the limitations of this study includes its geographic and institutional scope, as the sample was drawn exclusively from a single urban public trade school in Misamis Occidental, which may not represent learners from rural areas or different cultural regions. Additionally, while stratified sampling was utilized, the total sample size of 267 participants limits the generalizability of the results, particularly for specific subgroups such as definite morning or definite evening chronotypes. Furthermore, the study focused only on direct correlations and did not account for other mediating or moderating variables such as sleep quality, academic stress, digital device use, or family environment that typically influence both sleep-wake patterns and student wellbeing. Consequently, these factors necessitate caution when generalizing the findings to broader adolescent populations.

To build upon these findings, future research should utilize longitudinal designs and more diverse samples across various geographic and cultural contexts to enhance the

generalizability of the results. It is recommended that future studies investigate mediating and moderating variables such as sleep quality, academic stress, digital device use, and family environment, while also incorporating objective physiological measures to supplement self-reported data. For practical application, school administrators should design systems synchronized with intermediate chronotypes and enhance wellbeing programs that foster educational purpose and school connectedness. Guidance counselors are encouraged to prioritize psychosocial support services that address stress management, emotional regulation, and academic motivation, as these factors appear more influential to student wellbeing than biological sleep-wake preferences alone.

Note

Raw data of this study may be openly accessed through: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16530641>.

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Declaration of No Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no known financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. This research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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